

Systematic Review Protocol

This review protocol has been conducted following Shamseer & al. (2015) PRISMA-P preferred reporting items when applicable to a non-medical qualitative review.

Section 1: Administrative information

- 1a: Identification Professional entanglements: A qualitative systematic review of healthcare musicians' work in somatic hospital wards
- 1b: Update The protocol was created on Jan 29, 2019. For this version contact the authors. The protocol information was modified on December 2, 2019 as follows:
1a Identification: The title was subtly revised.
7 Aims and research questions: Subtly revised the wording of the questions. The protocol information was modified on June 25, 2019 as follows:
1a Identification: The title was revised.
3a Contact information: Revised, as one author withdraw from the review group.
3b Contributions: Clearer presentation of contributions was made and slightly revised.
7 Aims and research questions: Subtly revised the wording of the aims and questions according to the focus of the review. Added identified PICO(T) elements.
10 Search strategy and databases: Upgraded search strategy in electronic databases and search engines, which was conducted in February 2019.

Registration

- 2: Registration There is no direct outcome relevance to human health, and therefore this review does not meet the scope of the PROSPERO registrations, and is not registered.

Authors

- 3a: Contact information Corresponding author: Taru-Anneli Koivisto*, taru.koivisto@uniarts.fi
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- 3b: Contributions TAK is the guarantor. TT contributed to the development of the selection criteria, the risk of bias assessment strategy, and data extraction. Both authors will read, provide feedback and approve the final manuscript. Information specialist Harri Ollikainen from University of the Arts Helsinki developed the search strategy and the methodology section dealing with PRISMA methodology, along with the corresponding author. Heidi Westerlund, Tuulikki Laes, and Kai Lehtikainen from University of the Arts Helsinki provide their expertise as supervisors. MuTri doctoral school researchers from University of the Arts Helsinki provide their expertise as consulting researchers at the final stages of the review (ROBIS assessment and PRISMA checklist).

Amendments

- 4: Documenting amendments If we need to amend this protocol, we will give the date of each amendment, describe the change, and give the rationale in this section.

Support

- 5a: Sources This systematic review was undertaken as part of the Arts as Public Service: Strategic Steps towards Equality (ArtsEqual) Research Initiative supported by the Academy of Finland's Strategic Research Council (grant no. 314223/2017). The ethical statement for the study, which is a sub-

study of a doctoral dissertation of the main author, was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the Arts Helsinki (Feb 15, 2018).

5b: Sponsor The MuTri Doctoral School of Sibelius Academy and CERADA, University of the Arts Helsinki, are funding this review.

5c: Role of sponsor and/or funder The main authors have conducted the design of the project's protocol, analysis plan, the data collection, and analysis. The funders have had no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Section 2: Introduction

6: Rationale Despite the new kinds of professional views and spaces that musicians and music educators are encountering in healthcare settings, the research literature concerning their professionalism and the aims and goals of their practices in special healthcare services require more examination and conceptualization. However, professional views (beyond therapeutic goals) have remained scarcely researched, and music practices in hospital wards are mainly non-systematic. Hence, the increasing opportunities in novel sectors of society are also setting new goals for the research and education of music practitioners (ie. in this study healthcare musicians).

Objectives

7. Aim and research questions The aim of this qualitatively organized systematic review is to explore the research literature considering healthcare musicians' work and professional space in somatic healthcare wards in hospitals. PICO(T) elements include: defining the Problem/Patient/Population, Intervention/Indication, Comparison, Outcome, and optionally Time element or Type of study. In the following table, the PICO elements have been identified for the aim and rationale of this study.

P (Problem or Patient or Population)	Healthcare musicians
I (Intervention or indicator)	Work and professional space in hospital wards
C (Comparison)	Conceptual issues
O (Outcome of interest)	Professional practices

To this end, the proposed systematic review will answer the following questions:

1. What kind of professional practices and professional space are represented in the reviewed literature concerning healthcare musicians' work in somatic hospital wards?
2. According to the reviewed literature, in what ways can the work and professional space of healthcare musicians be conceptualized?

Section 3: Methods

Eligibility criteria

8. Study characteristics Studies will be selected according to the criteria outlined below:

Study designs: Peer-reviewed articles in scholarly journals are included; book chapters, reports, and grey literature overall are excluded. Articles that have a title or abstract referring exclusively to music therapy, music medicine, or music health and wellbeing outside of healthcare or hospital environments are also excluded.

Participants: For the purposes of the study, only articles that contribute to the professional work of educated music practitioners (i.e. musicians and music educators possessing a professional degree) are included. Both empirical and non-empirical, as well as qualitative, quantitative, and mixed

methods studies are included. Studies that refer to work in every kind of hospitals are included, i.e. children’s hospitals, adult’s hospitals, and elderly care hospitals. Hence, participants of the studies may address children, adults, and seniors.

Interventions: Of interest are interventions in the frame of community music, care music, health musicking, music education, and musicianship. Out of the scope of the research are music for self-care, music in non-professional (voluntary) use, music medicine, music therapy, and trans-professional learning in medicine through music. Articles with no interventions will also be included in the review process.

Comparators: Studies with any types of comparators or control types will be included.

Outcomes: Outcomes will be collected, analyzed and reported descriptively, and coded and synthesized through thematic analysis.

Timing: The timeframe of the search will be restricted between the years 2008-2018.

Setting: As stated earlier, healthcare settings will be included.

Language: Articles written in the English language will be included.

Information sources

9. Intended information sources

The preliminary search included hand-searching and harvesting of references, broadly including literature published between the years 2000-2018. Some authors were contacted to identify relevant studies.

Systematic search will be conducted by following PRISMA guidelines where applicable. Literature search strategies will be developed using medical subject headings (MeSH), the Finnish Thesaurus and Ontology Service (Finto), and Library of Congress Subject Headings (LSCH). Electronic search strategies will be developed with an information specialist.

Search strategy

10. Search strategy of databases

The preliminary stage will be conducted through various databases such as EBSCO, ProQuest, Finna, and Google Scholar. The titles and abstracts of the databases will be searched with PICO(T) mapped terms *music AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”), “music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”), (musician OR musicians) AND (hospital OR hospitals).*

In the systematic review search four electronic databases and/or search engines will be searched to identify eligible articles: Dimensions, ProQuest, Google Scholar and EBSCO. Keyword searches will include following Boolean phrase variations: *“music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”), (“care music” OR “health musicking”) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”), (musician OR musicians) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”).*

Updated information on June 25, 2019: Search strategy in electronic databases and search engines, conducted in February 2019.

Databases and search engines	Keywords	Filters and specific databases	Results	Evaluation
Dimensions	“music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Title and abstract; articles	5	Forward screening
ProQuest	“music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Anywhere except full text (NOFT); English; all databases; peer-reviewed scholarly journals; articles	43	Forward screening

Google Scholar	“music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018	11400	Too many irrelevant results*
EBSCO	“music education” AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; English; Peer-reviewed academic journals; Databases Academic Search Elite, ERIC, RILM	56	Forward screening
Dimensions	(“Care music” OR “health musicking”) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Title and abstract; articles	7	Music therapy; music medicine
ProQuest	(“Care music” OR “health musicking”) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Anywhere except full text (NOFT); English; all databases; peer-reviewed scholarly journals; articles	1	A duplicate
Google Scholar	(“Care music” OR “health musicking”) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018	1350	Impossible to specify filters; too many irrelevant results*
EBSCO	(“Care music” OR “health musicking”) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; English; Peer-reviewed academic journals; Databases Academic Search Elite, ERIC, RILM	8	Irrelevant results*
Dimensions	(Musician OR musicians) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Title and abstract; articles	51	Forward screening
ProQuest	(Musician OR musicians) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; Anywhere except full text (NOFT); English; all databases; peer-reviewed scholarly journal; articles	43	Forward screening
EBSCO	(Musician OR musicians) AND (hospital OR hospitals OR “health care”)	2008-2018; English; Peer-reviewed academic journals; Databases Academic Search Elite, ERIC, RILM	215	Too many irrelevant results*

* The results were duplicates, from the field of music and medicine, music therapy, and/or it was impossible to specify the filters considering included concepts.

Study records

11a: Data management	Reflows and Excel are used in the data management of this study. Paper copies of the articles will also be provided after the screening stage in the study selection and search process.
11b: Selection process	The selection of eligible articles will be conducted through a process of identification of relevant titles and abstracts. The review authors will independently screen the titles and abstracts yielded by the search against the inclusion criteria. After that, full-text articles will be screened first by main author TAK, and then by TT. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion or, when necessary, consulting the supervisory group of HW, TL, and KL. The reasons for excluding trials will be recorded and reported.
11c: Data collection process	The data abstracted will include demographic information, methodology, possible intervention details, and all reported patient-important outcomes.

Data items

12: Data search variables	<p>Studies, both graded and open access, meeting the inclusion criteria will be organized and coded using descriptive statistical analysis. Publication characteristics will also be extracted. The next level of analysis will then be conducted, combining top-down and bottom-up (Braun & Clarke, 2006) thematic analysis procedures.</p> <p>The following publication characteristics will be extracted: Author(s), journal, country where empirical data were collected, JUFO and SHERPA/RoMEO rating, Google Scholar citation rate of the article.</p> <p>Descriptive characteristics of the studies will be provided as follows: Studies with empirical data (data collection methods, data analysis methods, healthcare environment the study was conducted in, nature of music interventions and approaches) and studies with no empirical data (methodology, nature of approaches).</p> <p>For deeper qualitative analysis, the following data will be extracted on the basis of the research questions and their PICOT elements: 1) Professional skills and competence, 2) Other relevant skills and competences, 3) Professional practices, 4) Professional concepts, 5) Professional identity features, and 6) Alternative professional themes.</p>
Outcomes and prioritisation	
13: Primary and secondary outcomes	<p>The primary outcomes of the review will explore and conceptualize the work of healthcare musicians in hospital wards. Outcomes will also identify the professional approaches of music-making in somatic healthcare, and clarify the professional approaches of music making in healthcare settings.</p> <p>Secondary outcomes of the review will provide implications for future research and practices in the field. Secondary outcomes may also review the 'state of the art' in the research field related to the review, as well as enlighten the quality features of the research in the field.</p>
Risk of bias individual studies	
14: Assessment of risk of bias	<p>To facilitate the assessment of possible risk of bias for each study, the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP, 2018) will be used to summarize the quality appraisals across included studies.</p>
Data synthesis	
15a: Synthesis criteria	<p>Quantitative meta-analysis will not be conducted. The pre-understanding of the main author is that the results of the data search are variable in diverse and fragmented ways, as well as the hypothesis that there will not be enough data to conduct meta analyses. Heterogeneity will not be tested, nor any other quantitative methodology provided.</p>
15b: Summary criteria	<p>A narrative, qualitative summary will most probably be provided, and assessed beforehand to be the most relevant way to provide the key information of the review.</p>
15c: Additional analyses	<p>The data will be coded and analyzed thematically, firstly with conceptual sub-themes, following the concluding, consistent key theme of the review: professionalism. As a synthesizing conclusion, a suggestion for enhancing the professionalism of music practitioners in healthcare is presented.</p>
15d: Type of summary planned	<p>The findings of the review will be provided, along with discussion, a statement of the limitations of the study, an assessment of the bias of the review, and implications for future research.</p>
Meta-bias(es)	
16: Assessment of meta-bias(es)	<p>ROBIS (2018), a tool for assessing risk of bias in systematic reviews, will be used, when applicable to qualitative research. In addition to the authors, consulting researchers from University of the Arts Helsinki will assess the validity, consistency, and reliability of the review.</p>
Confidence in cumulative estimate	

17. Assessment of the body of evidence As well as the assessment of meta-bias, the quality of evidence for all outcomes will be judged by the authors, consulting researchers, and, if appropriate, by the use of a tool such as GRADE (The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation, 2018).

References:

CASP Critical appraisal skills programme. (2018). *CASP qualitative research checklist*. Retrieved from <https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/>.

Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., & Altman, D. G. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, *151*(4), 264–269. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-151-4-200908180-00135

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PRISMA. (2018). *Transparent reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses*. Retrieved from <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>.

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